

The role of convection and magnetic field in the mass loss of evolved cool stars

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Abstract

Red supergiants (RSG) and asymptotic giant branch (AGB) stars produce strong stellar winds, which are not well understood. These winds have a key role in the enrichment of the interstellar medium with chemical elements, which are the building blocks for the next generation of stars. The magnetic field in such stars coupled with the atmospheric dynamics may also affect the stellar wind, since it increases atmospheric velocities and higher temperatures in the chromosphere. The understanding of the stellar wind dynamics is crucial for unveiling the unknown mass-loss mechanism, their chemical composition, and their stellar parameters. The radiative-hydrodynamics code, CO5BOLD, solves the equations of compressible hydrodynamics and non-local radiation transport. It is used to produce 3D grids of global “star-in-a-box” models. In this ongoing study, we used CO5BOLD to perform simulations of RSG and AGB so we analyze and better understand the mechanisms and rate of mass-loss of such stars related to convection and magnetic field. We could compare the differences between our AGB and RSG models regarding density, velocity, pressure and B field, and found that magnetic fields could be part of the mass-loss mechanism in RSGs.

1 Introduction

Evolved cool stars, such as red supergiants (RSG) and asymptotic giant branch (AGB) stars, are major cosmic engines. They enrich their environment with chemical elements, which are the building blocks of the planets and life. RSG stars are late-type stars with effective temperature, T_{eff} , ranging from 3450 (M5) to 4100 K (K1), luminosities in the range of 2000 to 300,000 L_{\odot} , and radii up to 1500 R_{\odot} (Levesque *et al.*, 2005). Their which luminosities place them among the brightest stars, and they are visible up to very large distances (Chiavassa *et al.*, 2011). Detailed simulations of RSGs (Freytag *et al.*, 2002; Freytag & Höfner, 2008; Chiavassa *et al.*, 2009, 2010) show that these stars are characterized by vigorous convection, which imprints a pronounced granulation pattern on the stellar surface.

AGB stars are very bright, have a strong influence on integrated-light properties (Bruzual & Charlot, 2003), and are associated with characteristic phenomena such as pulsation, dust formation, and mass loss through massive stellar winds (Freytag & Höfner, 2008). These processes play an important role in the evolution and for observable properties of both individual cool giants and stellar systems since AGB stars are major contributors to the chemical enrichment of the interstellar medium and to the integrated light of galaxies.

Fusion reactions in the solar core releases energy which is transported outward by radiation up to 70 % of the solar radius, then further out primarily by convection up to the solar surface, and finally most of this energy is emitted in the form of radiation in the photosphere. The energy produced in the solar core is transported outward by radiation, then further out primarily by convection, and finally most of

this energy is emitted in the form of radiation in the photosphere. However, a small part of the energy is carried by waves and by magnetic fields, driving stellar activity phenomena in the solar chromosphere and corona (Freytag *et al.*, 2002; Wedemeyer-Böhm *et al.*, 2012). In RSGs and AGBs the internal structure is more complex, with several shells of nuclear fusion and multiple convection zones. To access the physical processes from the inner shells to the outer layers of stellar atmosphere, physical models of stars with a realistic treatment of both radiation and convection are essential.

It is crucial to have a detailed understanding of wind physics across the life cycle of these stars as well as in relation to their cosmic environment. Strong mass-loss may be related to the interplay of convective motions, acoustic waves, magnetic field, and radiation pressure on molecular lines and/or dust. Therefore, the main topics we investigate are: how the winds are launched and which physical processes determine their properties, and how do the mass-loss rate and other wind properties depend on fundamental stellar parameters. In this work-in-progress study, part of the ANR funded project PEPPER, we perform global simulations of evolved cool stars, including the magnetic field, and analysis of mechanisms related to winds and mass-loss of such stars, in to understand and characterize the link between convection and magnetic field in the stratification of stellar atmosphere.

2 Methodology

We performed global simulations (star-in-a-box setup) of a RSG and an AGB star. For that we use the COnservative COde for the COmputation of COmpressible COnvection in

Figure 1: Bolometric intensity (left panels) and magnetic field (center and right panels). The upper panels are for the AGB model and the lower panels are for the RSG model. *Left panels*: the white circle represents the apparent radius of the stars, which is an average over time, and it was defined where optical depth, $\tau = 1$, by the Rosseland approximation. Above the circles, there are the atmosphere and outer layers of the stars. *Center panels*: observer's line of sight component of the magnetic field, B_z . The white circle represents the apparent radius of the stars. *Right panels*: distribution of B field intensity, $|B| = \sqrt{B_x + B_y + B_z}$. Zero in x -axis is the center of the star, the red lines are the stellar radius, and the blue lines are the $|B|$ average over radius..

Figure 2: 2D representations of the parameters averages taken from 20 central slices over the z -axis: logarithm of density, $\log|\rho|$, logarithm of gas pressure, $|P_G|$, and logarithm of magnetic field intensity, $\log|B|$ for both the AGB (upper panels) and the RSG model (lower panels).

Figure 3: Radial velocity over radius (left panels), ratio of turbulent pressure and gas pressure, P_T / P_G , over radius (center panels), and Velocities over radius (right panels). The upper panels are for the AGB model and the lower panels are for the RSG model. *Left panels*: each line corresponds to a snapshot over the last 20 years (AGB) and 10 years (RSG) of the simulations. The cyan line corresponds to the no-B-field model, and the red lines are the stellar radius. *Center panels*: each line corresponds to a snapshot over the last 20 years (AGB) and 10 years (RSG) of the simulations. The red lines are the stellar radius. *Right panels*: velocities over radius (last snapshot). Black dots are radial velocity distribution, blue lines are sound speed, orange lines are radial velocity averages, green lines are Alfvén velocity, gray lines are escape velocity, and dashed red lines are stellar radius.

a BOx of L Dimensions (CO⁵BOLD; Freytag *et al.*, 2002; Freytag & Höfner, 2008; Freytag *et al.*, 2012; Riva & Steiner, 2022). This is a radiation magnetohydrodynamics (RMHD) code for the computation of compressible convection in a 3D box, that reproduces convective effects of the star, uses detailed microphysics under the conditions in stellar surface layers, and the equations of ideal magneto-hydrodynamics, including gravity and radiative energy exchange. The computational domain is a cubic grid, and the same open boundary condition is employed for all sides of the computational box.

In this work we are focused on the magnetic field influence on the models, since the presence of magnetic fields results in a wide range of additional complex 3D phenomena (Freytag *et al.*, 2012). Small-scale concentrations of magnetic flux lead to enhanced radiative losses, both in the photosphere and in the chromosphere (Freytag *et al.*, 2012). The interaction of convection and magnetic fields can be modeled in the framework of (ideal) MHD.

We use hydrodynamical (without magnetic fields) models that are already relaxed, *i.e.* simulations which the stellar parameters fluctuations are stable. Then we add an initial torus-shaped magnetic field close to the center of the star of 0.5 G and run the simulations until the magnetic energy saturates. The AGB model refers to a star of $1 M_{\odot}$, $7000 L_{\odot}$, $393 R_{\odot}$, T_{eff} of 2660 K, $\log g$ of -0.75 , and spatial resolution of 317^3 grid points. The RSG model has the following parameters: $5 M_{\odot}$, $41,200 L_{\odot}$, $594 R_{\odot}$, T_{eff} of 3370 K, $\log g$ of -0.41 , and spatial resolution of 315^3 grid points. The simulated time were respectively 42 and 25 years, which were the necessary period for the simulation to get stable stellar parameters. The bolometric intensities and radii of both models are shown in the left panels in Figure 1.

3 Preliminary Results and Discussion

The convection cells of the AGB model are larger than those of the RSG model, due to a lower mass and also the radius (left panels in Figure 1). The size of the convective surface cells relative to the stellar radius scales well with R_{\star} / M_{\star} . Temperature, energy and $\log g$ are lower, as pressure scale height is higher, which makes the AGB to have a more diluted atmosphere. The magnetic field is higher and more concentrated in the center of the AGB model (center and right panels in Figure 1).

Figure 2 shows the logarithm of density, $\log |\rho|$, logarithm of gas pressure, $\log |P_G|$, logarithm of magnetic field intensity, $\log |B|$, for both the AGB (left panels) and the RSG model (right panels). These 2D representations are the parameters averages taken from 20 central slices over the z -axis. One may observe that shock waves happens where the $\log \rho$ and $\log P_G$ decreases. Similar patterns can be seen in $\log |B|$, due to the convection-magnetic connection.

Regarding the P_T / P_G ratio (center panels in Figure 3) the AGB model shows higher increase above the radius than the RSG model, however it is lower in the outer layers of the stellar atmosphere. Radial velocity decreases right above the radius and increase in the outer layers, steeper in the RSG model (left panels in Figure 3). In the non-magnetic AGB model (cyan line) radial velocity has a lower increase in the outer layers compared to the model with magnetic field. That may indicate the magnetic fields play a significant role for the wind-formation process. Also, above the radius in the AGB model the Alfvén velocities are higher than in the RSG model (right panels in Figure 3). However, in the AGB's outer layers it decreases whereas it increases in the RSG.

4 Final Considerations

This is a work in progress and we are running different models with different initial magnetic fields. The next steps of our work are (a) to improve the grid of simulated models regarding different magnetic fields intensity and directions, and different boundary conditions, (b) to create a grid of models to provide spectropolarimetric observables in the framework of PEPPER, and (c) to investigate how magnetic field impacts the outer layers stratification: velocity, density, mass-loss.

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